

Mediating Effect of Team Attitude on the Relationship between Transformational Leadership of School Heads Andteacher's Readiness for Organizational Change

Marisol C. Bantillo¹, Rinante L. Genuba²

¹Student, Professional Schools, University of Mindanao, Philippines

²Professor, Professional Schools, University of Mindanao, Philippines

ABSTRACT: This study determined the mediating effect of team attitude on the relationship between transformational leadership of school heads and teacher's readiness for organizational change in public elementary schools of Island Garden City of Samal. The quantitative research design was utilized bearing a sample of 300 elementary teachers of Island Garden City of Samal. Three set of adapted survey questionnaires were used to gather the target respondents' data. These instruments were subjected for content validity and reliability test. The analysis data was done using the Mean and Pearson r Correlation Coefficient and Path Analysis. The results revealed that the levels of transformational leadership of school heads, teacher's readiness for organizational change and team attitude were high. There was significance in the relationship between the transformational leadership of school heads and teacher's readiness for organizational change, leadership behaviors of school heads, and leadership behaviors of school heads and team attitude. Furthermore, a significant partial mediation of team attitude on the relationship between transformational leadership of school heads and teacher's readiness for organizational change was proven in the present study.

KEYWORDS: team attitude, transformational leadership of school heads, teacher's readiness for organizational change, educational management, Philippines

I. INTRODUCTION

Teachers' readiness to adapt with new implementations affect their attitudes, behaviors, and beliefs specially towards organizational change. In this situation, the problematic concern flourishes when teachers are faced with uncertainty, stress, and worry which are products of his/her weak or poor readiness in adapting and shifting to new implementations. When there are new policy implementations, when there are group tasks needed, and yet teachers are not ready, are just a few of the experiences that teacher have which tests their flexibility and readiness to adapt to changes around the workplace (Murzi, Chowdhury, Karlovšek, & Ulloa, 2020). Several pieces of literature consistently highlight that one of the essential elements of a team is its focus toward a common goal and a clear purpose (Rahamat, Shah, Din, & Abd Aziz, 2017). Yet, there are instances when teachers and school heads do not meet in their beliefs and practices making it an issue to teachers who are not willing to conform with the practices of their school heads. As emphasized in the study of Klar, Huggins, Andreoli and Buskey (2020) teachers readiness to new practices as mandated by its administrators influence productivity and performance. When new implementations are observed, and teachers are not ready for it, organizational conditions can be at risk ((Yeigh, Lynch, Turner, Provost, Smith & Willis, 2019).

The conduct of this study is important especially in today's shift in learning modalities as brought by the pandemic. Teachers' readiness for organizational change is essential for their professional growth, the improvement of student outcomes, and the overall success of educational institutions in a dynamic and evolving landscape. It is to note that the field of education is constantly evolving with new pedagogical approaches, technologies, and methodologies hence, teachers need to be ready for organizational changes to effectively incorporate these trends into their teaching practices (Al-Furaih & Al-Awidi, 2020; Leacock & Warrican, 2020).

Leadership and readiness to organizational changes among employees are seen as significant as transformational leadership is associated with increased levels of performance and helping behaviors in most schools as teachers continue to struggle in preparing and in sustaining the new normal learning delivery system (Leacock & Warrican, 2020). In fact, the study of Asbari, Hidayat and Purwanto (2021) showed that transformational leadership had a significant effect on readiness for change, when employees rated how their supervisors imposed practices. As stated in the study, employees who are not amiable of the the new policies where seen to have poor performance in delivering good outputs.

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II. METHOD

The study's respondents were the 300 public school teachers of the Island Garden City of Samal. A stratified random sampling design was used to determine the respondents in each school as the researcher wanted to know the effect of attitude on the relationship between the transformational leadership of school heads and teachers' readiness for organizational change. This is the best fit sampling so as to ensure the characteristics or attributes that might influence the mediating effects (Nguyen, Shih, Srivastava, Tirthapura & Xu, 2021). Specifically, the study was conducted at the Public Schools at Babak District, Island Garden City of Samal. For the inclusion criterion of the respondents, only the permanent public school teachers were invited to participate in this study. Additionally, these teachers are only from the Babak District schools. For the exclusion criterion, teachers from private schools, substitute public teachers, and school heads were excluded from the study.

This study used survey questionnaires to gather data. The questionnaire is a structured type and it is divided into three parts. The first part is the transformational leadership of school heads, and its subscales are charisma, social, vision, transactional, delegation, and execution, which is from Clark (2011). For the scaling range for this part, 3.41- 4.00 is described as definitely true. For 2.61- 3.40, it is probably true. Next for 1.81-2.60, it is described as definitely true. Lastly, for 1.00-1.80, it is described as Probably true. The second part is the teacher's readiness for organizational change from Shah(2009). The range of scale for 5.81-7.00 is described as very likely; for 5.00- 5.80, it is described as likely. For the range of 4.21-5.00, it is described as Somewhat likely. Then for the range 3.41-4.20, it is described as neither likely nor unlikely. Next for the range of 2.61- 3.40, it is described as somewhat unlikely. Then for the range, 1.81-2.60, it is described as unlikely. Finally, for 1.00-1.80, it is described as very unlikely. The last part is the teamwork survey instrument from Baker, Horvarth, Campion, Offermann, & Salas (2005). In this survey, the respondents put a check in the box, which could indicate their response in each statement stated in the instrument. The range of scale from 4.21- 5.00 is described as strongly agree, 3.41-4.20 is described as Agree, 2.61-3.40 is described as neither agree nor disagree, 1.81-2.60 is described as disagree, 1.00-1.80 is described as strongly disagree. The validation process included seeking the comments of the validators in enhancing and modifying the adapted questionnaires. After the validation process, a Cronbach alpha testing was conducted where it resulted to a value of 0.968 for leadership, 0.966 for readiness, and 0.899 for team attitude which further means that instrument follows within the standard validity with Cronbach Alpha Coefficients higher than 0.700 hence, it was prompted for administration.

The researcher used the descriptive-correlation research design. According to Wagner (2014) this design best fits this study as this involves collecting data on the level of team attitude, transformational leadership skill and teachers' readiness in order to determine whether the relationships exist. With this, the relationship between transformational leadership of school heads and teacher's readiness for organizational change was correlated and that the mediating effect of team attitude was also studied through the use of path analysis.

For the data gathering procedure, these were undertaken, first, the checking and examining of letter. The gathering of data started by consulting the adviser to check the letter if it is precise for the further request of the study. Then, the Signing of letters for administration. Afterwards, the Refining of Research Survey Questionnaire followed through the help of the adviser and the validators. Next step was the Asking of permission from the Division Schools Superintendent and the school principals. When the request was granted, the researcher conducted the study in the chosen Public Elementary Schools. Right away, the researcher administered the survey questionnaires to the respondents at a given schedule. It took more than 3 days to completely administer the questionnaire to the respondents. Then, the retrieval of questionnaire followed and the survey questionnaires were collected after the respondents were done answering it. Lastly, the tabulation, analysis, and interpretation of data was completed, the scores were subjected to tabulation. Moreover, the data were interpreted and analyzed with the help of the statistician and the adviser.

This study used the mean, Pearson r Correlation Coefficient and the multiple regression. For the Mean, this was used to determine the average score of the two variables. To calculate the mean of a set of data, it must first add up (sum) all of the data values (x) and then divide the result by the number of values (n). For the Pearson r correlation coefficient, this was used to determine the relationship between the Transformational Leadership and Teachers Readiness for Organizational Change. Lastly, the multiple regression was used in determining the mediating effect of attitude in the relationship between Transformational Leadership and Teachers Readiness for Organizational Change. Testing of null hypothesis was tested on $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Level of transformational leadership of school heads

Presented in Table 1 is the level of Transformational Leadership of School heads which gained an an SD of 0.30 and an overall mean score of 4.45 described as very high. It can also be gleaned in the table that all indicators got the same descriptive equivalent of very high but with minimal differences in their garnered mean scores and Standard Deviation. The lowest mean was from the indicator Delegation which garnered a mean score of 4.34 and a standard deviation of 0.58. interpreted as very high. This further means that even if the results reveal similar verbal descriptions of very high, the specific mean scores differ and that delegation

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being the lowest of all can be interpreted that the school heads may have some points to improve in terms of delegating tasks to their teachers.

The very high level of Transformational Leadership among school heads can then be associated with what Carver-Thomas, Leung and Burns (2021) mentioned that transformational leaders are able to connect with the follower's sense of identity and self to the mission and the collective identity of the organization; being a role model for followers that inspires them; challenging followers to take greater ownership for their work, and understanding the strengths and weaknesses of followers, so the leader can align followers with tasks that optimize their performance. These attributes are manifested by the school heads hence, teachers see them to possess a very high transformational leadership skill.

Table 1. Level of transformational leadership of school heads

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Charisma	0.55	4.40	Very High
Social	0.47	4.45	Very High
Vison	0.48	4.48	Very High
Transactional	0.43	4.49	Very High
Delegation	0,58	4.34	Very High
Execution	0.44	4.53	Very High
Overall	0.30	4.45	Very High

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The current study result also resembles with the study results of Purwanto (2022) which highlighted that execution is an indicator of transformational leadership is the most visible barometer to assess the leadership skill of a leader. In this study, this indicator got the highest mean score and most teachers rated their school head here as very high. This is a manifestation that the school heads have very visible performance which even gave their teachers the feeling of getting motivated and determined as well to persevere serving well in their duties.

B. Level of teacher’s readiness for organizational change

Presented in Table 2 is the level of teachers’ readiness to organizational change, which gained an overall standard deviation of 0.37 and mean of 4.34, which is interpreted as very high. The significant values that can be noted in the table are that in the indicators, Solving university problems and finding ways to make the change fail, these only got a mean score of 4.17 and 3.78, interpreted as high.

The level of teachers’ readiness for organizational change is very high. This means that teachers perceive that they are ready for organizational changes. Learning new things and manifesting motivation to improve performance are the indicators that got the highest mean score.

This result is a good attribute, as emphasized in the study of Chonk (2020), which stipulated the significance of having employees who are open to organizational changes. Having employees of this kind follows a good working environment, which, according to the study results of Barnett and Carroll (2019), employees normally feel happy and challenged when change happens in an organization, yet, with their positive thoughts towards the institution, they can just adjust and accept it.

Table 2. Level of Readiness in Organizational Change

Items	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Doing things in a new or creative way.	0.60	4.47	Very High
Changing the way I work because of the change.	0.59	4.40	Very High
Taking responsibility for the change if it fails in my area.	0.61	4.37	Very High
Being a part of the change program.	0.62	4.49	Very High
Learning new things.	0.66	4.56	Very High
Changing something even if it appears to be working.	0.70	4.24	Very High
Supporting change.	0.66	4.40	Very High

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Improving what we are currently doing rather than implement a major change.	0.65	4.39	Very High
Selling ideas about the change.	0.66	4.32	Very High
Telling people who it is I work for.	0.73	4.27	Very High
Working more because of the change.	0.68	4.41	Very High
Solving university problems.	0.77	4.17	High
Being a part of the new project.	0.69	4.31	Very High
Creating new ideas.	0.84	4.21	Very High
Finding ways to make the change fail.	1.36	3.78	High
Communicating well with my school head.	0.63	4.42	Very High
Respecting my boss’s judgment on my issue.	0.71	4.32	Very High
Knowing that my work had contributed to the good of the school would please me.	0.66	4.41	Very High
Improving my performance when my school head shows me how to do so.	0.60	4.48	Very High
Knowing what is expected of me.	0.67	4.42	Very High
Overall	0.37	4.34	Very High

C. Level of attitude of the school heads in terms of team Attitude Competencies

Presented in Table 3 is the level of attitude in terms of team attitude competence which gained an overall standard deviation of 0.34 and an overall mean score of 4.49 interpreted as very high. It can be gleaned from the data that in all indicators, similar result of very high level was presented. This means that in all ways, the school heads possess a very high team attitude in showing off their competencies.

Table 3. Level of Team Attitude Competencies

Items	SD	Me an	Descriptive Level
Believing that teamwork skills deserve more attention in the workplace	0.65	4.45	Very High
Believing that teams make better decisions than individuals	0.65	4.50	Very High
Giving a choice, I would rather work alone than do a job where I have to work in a team.	1.00	4.25	Very High
Believing that it is impossible to function in today’s society without being a good team player.	0.71	4.40	Very High
Preferring to participate in team-oriented activities.	0.70	4.42	Very High
Believing that teams always outperform individuals.	0.74	4.33	Very High
Believing that everyone should be taught to be a good team player	0.61	4.50	Very High
Preferring to work on teams where team members perform their tasks independently rather than working together.	0.83	4.37	Very High
Finding that working as a member of a team increases my ability to perform effectively.	0.66	4.45	Very High
Finding working in a team to be very satisfying.	0.61	4.53	Very High
Believing that teamwork is one of the most important life skills.	0.66	4.51	Very High
Preferring to be rewarded for my team’s performance rather than my performance.	0.64	4.51	Very High
Believing that people with strong teamwork skills always be successful.	0.66	4.59	Very High

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Believing that teams plan better than individuals.	0.73	4.53	Very High
Preferring working as part of a team to working alone.	0.73	4.48	Very High
Believing that there should have positive attitudes toward teamwork.	0.65	4.53	Very High
Believing that there should have mutual trust among team members.	0.66	4.57	Very High
Finding that higher levels of mutual trust among team members led to a more harmonious and productive team environment.	0.50	4.69	Very High
Believing that an attraction to being part of a team has enhanced team process and performance.	0.59	4.57	Very High
Believing that attitudes toward teamwork can significantly affect how teamwork skills are put into practice.	0.69	4.56	Very High
Overall	0.34	4.49	Very High

The level of attitude of school heads in terms of team attitude competencies is very high. The statements which garnered the highest mean scores were all about , Believing that people with strong teamwork skills always be successful; Believing that there should have mutual trust among team members ; and Believing that an attraction to being part of a team has enhanced team process and performance. It can be surmised that the teacher perceived a positive attitude towards their school heads as their responses conforms with the study results of Barilan (2021) and Jose (2019) which emphasize that a positive working environment promotes productivity especially when teachers are trusted to work in a team.

This study result also confirms the usual study results present in the papers of Driskell and Salas (2019) which point out the positive attitudes toward teamwork and mutual trust among team members are examples of critical attitudes related to team process found that higher levels of mutual trust among team members led to a more harmonious and productive team environment.

D. Significant relationship between transformational leadership of school heads and teacher’s readiness for organizational change

Presented in Table 4.1 is the significant relationship drawn between Transformational Leadership of school heads and teachers’ readiness to organizational change. It gained an overall r value of 0.537 which manifests a significant correlation between the variables mentioned. This further suggests the rejection of the hypothesis saying that there is no relationship between Transformational Leadership of schools and teachers’ readiness to organizational change.

Table 4.1. Significance on the Relationship between Transformational Leadership and Readiness for Organizational Change

Transformational Leadership	Readiness for Organizational Change
Charisma	.302** .000
Social	.226** .000
Vision	.356** .000
Transactional	.391** .000
Delegation	.337** .000
Execution	.403** .000
Overall	.537** .000

The overall result manifests a significant correlation between transformational leadership of school heads and teachers’ readiness for organizational change. This means that the independent variable is strongly related to the dependent variable and this result corroborates with the study results of Paschen and Dihsmailer, (2019)which stated that transactional leaders are effective in getting specific tasks completed by managing each portion individually. And that, transactional leaders are concerned with processes rather than forward-thinking ideas, making it more effective for its co-workers to accept and adapt with changes that are implemented in the workstation.

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Further, in this study, it was also emphasized that the teachers, even if they sometimes encounter problems in terms of delegation, they still see more of the positive side of their school heads which make them still effective and open to changes. This manifests positive attitude towards changes which conforms with success of organizational change is often determined by employee attitudes and beliefs towards the change (Beer & Walton, 2020).

E. Significant relationship between transformational leadership of school heads and Team Attitude Competencies Presented in Table 4.2 is the significant relationship between transformational leadership of school heads and Team Attitude Competencies which shows a correlation of .372 and is highly statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating that there is a positive relationship between Transformational Leadership as a whole and Team Attitude Competencies.

Table 4.2 Significance on the Relationship between Transformational Leadership and Team Attitude Competencies

Transformational Leadership	Team Attitude Competencies
Charisma	.222** .000
Social	.131* .024
Vision	.263** .000
Transactional	.200** .000
Delegation	.320** .000
Execution	.228** .000
Overall	.372** .000

A positive correlation is indicated by a positive number, and a negative correlation is indicated by a negative number. The strength of the correlation is indicated by the absolute value of the number. In the table, Charisma (.222) has a moderately positive correlation with Team Attitude Competencies. Social (.131) has a positive correlation, though it is somewhat weaker. Vision (.263) has a stronger positive correlation. Transactional (.200) also has a moderately positive correlation. Delegation (.320) has the strongest positive correlation. Execution (.228) has a moderately positive correlation as well. This means that all the correlations are statistically significant at the 0.05 level, suggesting that there is a relationship between Transformational Leadership components and Team Attitude Competencies. In summary, the table suggests that Transformational Leadership, as well as its individual components, is positively and significantly correlated with Team Attitude Competencies. The stronger the correlation value, the stronger the relationship. These results indicate that Transformational Leadership practices are associated with higher levels of Team Attitude Competencies in the context of the study.

The overall result of having significant relationship between transformational leadership of school heads and organizational change in terms of attitude. Overall, the result confirms that attitude of people in a team reflects groups of people with complementary skills who are committed to a common purpose and hold themselves mutually accountable for its achievement. Ideally, they develop a distinct identity and work together in a coordinated and mutually supportive way to fulfil their goal or purpose. Task effectiveness is the extent to which the team is successful in achieving its task-related objectives. Shared goals are most likely to be achieved through working together and pooling experience and expertise (Mulika, 2020).

F. Significant relationship between Team Attitude and teacher’s readiness for organizational change Presented in Table 4.3 is the significant relationship between Team Attitude Competencies and Teachers’ Readiness for organizational change which gained a p- value of 0.371. This means that the individual capacities of the variables significantly matters. Hence, the rejection of the hypothesis.

Table 4.3 Significance on the Relationship between Team Attitude Competencies and Teacher’s readiness for organizational change

Team Attitude Competencies	Readiness for Organizational Change
Overall	.371** .000

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The correlation coefficient of .371 is a measure of the strength and direction of the relationship between Team Attitude Competencies and Readiness for Organizational Change. In this case, the positive value (.371) suggests a positive correlation, indicating that higher levels of Team Attitude Competencies are associated with higher levels of "Readiness for Organizational Change.

The p-value of .000 indicates that the observed correlation is highly statistically significant. A p-value of .000 essentially means that the relationship between Team Attitude Competencies and Readiness for Organizational Change is very unlikely to be due to random chance. This suggests a strong and meaningful connection between these two variables.

In summary, the table suggests that there is a positive and highly statistically significant relationship between Team Attitude Competencies and Readiness for Organizational Change. It implies that when a team demonstrates higher levels of attitude competencies, they are more likely to be prepared and ready for organizational changes.

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Based on the presented table and figures below, the mediation result is considered partial as the presence of a significant indirect effect is an indication of mediation. In this case, Team Attitude appears to mediate the relationship between Transformational Leadership and Organizational Change because both the direct path from Transformational Leadership to Organizational Change and the indirect path through Team Attitude are statistically significant. This suggests that part of the influence of Transformational Leadership on Organizational Change is explained by its impact on Team Attitude.

Specifically, there is a Direct Effect observed to Transformational Leadership on Organizational Change as indicated the first regression weight shows the relationship between Transformational Leadership and Organizational Change. The estimate is 0.662, and it is statistically significant (C.R. = 11.021). This suggests that there is a strong direct effect of Transformational Leadership on Organizational Change.

Further, there were also Direct and Indirect Effects to Transformational Leadership on Organizational Change via Team Attitude as the subsequent regression weights involve the mediator Team Attitude and its relationship with both Transformational Leadership and Organizational Change. Hence, Team Attitude mediates the relationship between Transformational Leadership and Organizational Change as the estimate for Team Attitude regressed on Transformational Leadership is 0.417, and it is statistically significant (C.R. = 6.936).

The estimate for Organizational Change regressed on Transformational Leadership while controlling for Team Attitude is 0.571, and it is also statistically significant (C.R. = 9.039).

The estimate for Organizational Change regressed on Team Attitude is 0.219, and it is statistically significant (C.R. = 3.879).

Table 5 Mediation Analysis of the Three Variables

Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
OrganizationalChange	<--- TransformationalLeadership	.662	.060	11.021	***	

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**PARTIAL
MEDIATION**

Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
TeamAttitude	<---	TrasformationalLeadership	.417	.060	6.936	***	
OrganizationalChange	<---	TrasformationalLeadership	.571	.063	9.039	***	
OrganizationalChange	<---	TeamAttitude	.219	.056	3.879	***	

Figure 2. Path Diagram for the Regression

In summary, the table and the figures indicate that Transformational Leadership has a significant direct effect on Organizational Change, and part of this effect is mediated by Team Attitude. This suggests that Transformational Leadership impacts Organizational Change both directly and indirectly through its influence on Team Attitude.

Transformational Leadership is indeed often associated with influencing organizational change, and Team Attitude can play a significant role in facilitating and mediating this influence. Contemporary leaders face a multitude of challenges when assuming their roles as catalysts of transformation. The pressing issue for leaders in this context is the profound uncertainty and rapid fluctuations inherent in a dynamic environment, making the mobilization of organizational change an arduous task. To ensure the establishment of organizational improvement and sustainability, it becomes imperative for leaders to embrace a strategic approach in effecting organizational change. This article examines the efficacy of transformational leadership as a model for driving organizational change within the contemporary leadership landscape. While debates persist regarding the most influential leadership style for instigating change, previous research outcomes have consistently validated transformational leadership as a distinctive and effective approach for achieving success in organizational change endeavors in today's ever-evolving environment(Usman, 2020; Bayraktar & Jiménez, 2020; Bagga, Gera & Haque, 2023).

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The very high level of transformational leadership of school heads, teachers’ readiness to organizational change, and attitude of the school heads in terms of team Attitude Competencies signify a good manifestation of how good school leaders are as perceived by the teachers. Further, the significant relationship observed between transformational leadership of school heads and teachers’ readiness to organization change also exhibits a positive working environment among the teacher respondents and their school heads as they see no problem in having changes in the workplace. This study result is in adherence to the proposition of Salas (2005) in his Big Five theory which explains the 5 components with 3 coordinating mechanisms. (1) Adaptability. It is the ability to adjust strategies based on information gathered from the environment through the use of backup behavior and reallocation of intra-team resources. Altering a course of action or team repertoire in response to changing conditions (internal or external); (2) Backup behavior. It is the ability to anticipate other team members’ needs through accurate knowledge about their responsibilities. This includes the ability to shift workload among members to achieve balance during high periods of workload or pressure; (3) Closed-loop communication. It is the exchange of information between a sender and a receiver irrespective of the medium; (4) Mutual performance monitoring. It is the ability to develop common understandings of the team environment and apply appropriate task strategies to accurately monitor teammate performance; (5) Mutual trust. It is the shared belief that team members will perform their roles and protect the interests of their teammates; (6) Shared mental models. It is an organizing knowledge structure of the

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relationships among the task the team is engaged in and how the team members will interact; (7) Team leadership. It is the ability to direct and coordinate the activities of other team members, assess team performance, assign tasks, develop team knowledge, skills, and abilities, motivate team members, plan and organize, and establish a positive atmosphere; and (8) Team orientation. It is the propensity to take other's behavior into account during group interaction and the belief in the importance of team goals over individual members' goals.

After a thorough analysis, it is recommended that teachers must be supplemented with series of trainings so they can sustain changes in their workstations. Nonetheless, even if the results reveal a very high level of teachers' readiness to change, still the transformational leadership of school heads must be continually studied to ensure a continuous progress in the schools that they are assigned. Trainings could be in a form of a retooling for teachers and school heads about the recent initiatives of the Department of Education which goals are intended to better the learning delivery system for public schools. Also, further studies can be explored which can be in form of a qualitative study on the experiences and insights of teachers in their continued journey towards transferring knowledge to their students especially as the department has shifted to face to face learning delivery.

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